

THE DIFFERENCES IN THE INFLUENCE OF MICROFINANCE BANK'S SOCIAL AND FINANCIAL INTERMEDIATION ACTIVITIES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SMALL-SCALE FOOD MANUFACTURING BUSINESSES IN LAGOS AND OYO STATES, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated micro-finance banks' social and financial intermediation activities on the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Nigeria. It aims to analyze the differences in the influence of microfinance banks' social and financial intermediation activities on the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo states, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlation descriptive survey design. A purposive sampling method was employed in the selection of seven hundred and forty-seven (747) small-scale food manufacturing businesses within Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria. Findings show that there is no significant relative difference in the effect of Microfinance Bank's social and financial intermediation activities on the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria. This study reveals that Microfinance banks' intermediations activities have a relative effect on their performances. Microfinance Banks' social intermediation has higher relative effects on the Performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector compared to Microfinance Banks' financial intermediation in the food manufacturing sector. The study recommends that federal government agencies, microfinance banks, and non-governmental organizations should initiate regular intermediations functions through managerial skills development, credit access, loans, saving schemes, seminars, and workshops to improve the small-scale food manufacturing businesses' performance in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria.

Keywords: Microfinance banks (MFBs), Microfinance Institutions (MFIs), Small and Medium Enterprises (SME) Social Intermediation, Financial Intermediation, Small-scale businesses, Small-scale business Performance, Credit Policies, Financial Services, and Social Services.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, the practice of microfinance is firmly established in culture and predates the rise of contemporary banks. Traditional microfinance organizations give low-income people access to money in both urban and rural locations. Informally run self-help groups (SHG) or rotating savings and credit associations (ROSCA) make up the majority of them. There are unauthorized financial organizations throughout the country, and they take the form of well-

established groups that work together for the benefit of their members. For Nigeria's micro- and small-business owners, the informal financial sector is a significant source of funding. This situation provides informal institutions with a platform to attempt to fill the gap left by official social networks. In many countries, people have relied on trade's capacity for mutual benefit and benefit-sharing the social networking of these areas to satisfy economic, social, and cultural requirements and enhance the quality of life (Portes, 1998).

Microfinance banks' primary function is to provide financial intermediation. The transfer of capital or liquidity from those who have an excess to those who are in deficit is covered by this. This is based on the notion that production and consumption do not occur concurrently, making financial intermediation the magic bullet required to connect these two extremes. Von (1991), who believed that finance in the form of savings and credit primarily permits coordination, further supports this position. Savings and credit are made more efficient and streamlined when intermediaries start transferring money from companies and people who have acquired money while also being willing to give up liquidity to those who need liquidity.

While it is obvious that microfinance institutions (MFIs) contribute to financial sustainability and monetary liquidity, it is not apparent whether microfinance in its current form aids in the fight against poverty or provides the best means of rural development. As financial intermediaries, MFIs have done a remarkable job, especially in terms of reviving the financial sector in rural areas. However, they must advance into social intermediation agents to combine microfinance and social capital. The social intermediation methods or microfinance drives are expected to widen their scope to and inside less fortunate fragments of the populace, particularly ladies, and have a different worth all by themselves by well upgrading the social capital of the members of microfinance institutions by delivering the genuine capability of its individuals through friendly intermediation. MFIs broadened the scope of the services they provided from financial intermediation to include social intermediation aimed at organized organizations and MSEs to increase their clientele and improve the business success of their clients (Han, 2009). Social intermediation activities have significantly impacted small-scale enterprise survival even though they were only intended to add distinctiveness to service delivery.

2. CONCEPT OF MICROFINANCE BANKS IN NIGERIA

2.1. Brief History of Microfinance banks in Nigeria

With the introduction of the microfinance policy by the former CBN governor Professor Chukwuma Soludo in 2005, microfinance banking came into existence. This policy was brought about by microfinance's highly regarded ability to help the working population escape poverty, which significantly reduced the degree of poverty. With the hope that it would eventually help reduce the degree of poverty in the nation, microfinance banking was subsequently founded. Subsequently, as expressed in segment 4:2:1 of the microfinance strategy, the arrangement objective incorporates accommodating most of the ruined however working populace continuously 2020 to make numerous business and decrease neediness.

Community banks were replaced by microfinance banks, which were founded and licensed by the CBN to achieve this. It is important to note that the Central Bank of Nigeria regulates more than 900 microfinance institutions in Nigeria today (Acha, 2012).

2.2 Functions of Microfinance Banks

In Nigeria, small- and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are served by microfinance banks, which offer all of the banking and financial services that megabanks offer. In essence, they provide services to the underprivileged to reduce poverty, and they also work to enhance SMEs and build their businesses. As a result, they provide their consumers with traditional banking services. Traditional and improved savings accounts, current accounts, fixed deposits, investment accounts, credit or lending products like overdrafts, leases, term loans of various terms but primarily start tenured trading loans, salary advances, LPO financing, etc. are some of the fundamental tools used by microfinance banks. Additionally, they provide support services like financial advice, feasibility reports, financial training, micro insurance, and local and international money transfers together with their corresponding banks, domestically and internationally. Small pensions, capacity development, etc. A reputable microfinance institution would be unlikely to make a loan without providing its client with some sort of support service (Thom-Otuya, 2014).

2.3 Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

According to SMEDAN (2017), micro-enterprises are companies with a total workforce of no more than 10 employees and assets totalling less than N10 million (excluding land and buildings). Independent companies are characterized as those with an all-out labour force of more than ten however less than 49 representatives and complete resources (barring area and structures) of more than N10 million yet under N100 million. Alternatively, medium-sized businesses are those with total assets (excluding land and buildings) of more than N50 million but less than N1 billion and a workforce of between 50 and 199 employees. The SME sub-sector has employed a total of 59,647,954 people, which represents 76.5% of the country's workforce and 7.64% of Nigeria's export revenues. The youth population must be reoriented to achieve the best possible migration from a job-seeking attitude to one of jobs-and-wealth creation, which raises the unresolved issue of additional inclusive involvement in this subsector by this group. The need for increasing youth involvement in SMEs and entrepreneurship cannot be overstated in a country with a population of over 190 million people, over 65% of whom are under the age of 35.

Table 1: Number of Small and Medium Enterprises by Sector, 2017

INDUSTRIES	SMALL	MEDIUM	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
Manufacturing	16,322	772	17,094	23.0
Mining & Quarrying	172	28	200	0.3
Accommodation & Food Services	5,940	168	6,108	8.4
Agriculture	386	0	386	0.5
Wholesale/Retail Trade	12,889	241	13,130	18.0
Construction	423	83	506	0.7
Transport & Storage	699	49	748	1.0
Information and Communication	573	48	621	0.8
Education	19,587	132	19,719	27.0
Administrative & Support Service Activities	956	15	971	1.3
Arts, Entertainment and Recreation	188	1	189	0.3
Other Services Activities	1,924	34	1,958	2.7
Water Supply, Sewage Water Management	9	0	9	0.0
Real Estate Activities	1,073	0	1,073	1.5
Human Health & Social Works	7,377	219	7,596	10.4
Professional, Scientific and Technical Works	2,772	1	2,773	3.8
TOTAL	71,288	1,793	73,081	100

Source: NBS-SMEDAN National Survey of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (Small scale business), 2017.

2.2.2 Small and Medium Enterprises Performance

Researchers in the field of management has utilized and advanced a variety of measuring parameters of SME performance, with each being more suitable and practical in a certain situation or situation. Particularly when the population comprises manufacturing businesses, performance should be judged in terms of output (Adebayo, et al., 2013; Luper & Kwanum, 2012; Obokoh, 2008). However, achieving organizational goals should be the primary criterion for assessing the performance of SMEs (Owoseni & Adeyeye, 2012). As a result, an accurate assessment of SMEs' performance should take into account the owner's goal or a policy intended to support SMEs in particular results areas, such as output and profitability (Marr & Schiuma, 2003). The effectiveness and financial outcomes of SMEs are frequently understood from a quantitative standpoint, level of production, customer count (Anggadwita & Mustafid, 2014), market share, profit, productivity, dynamics of revenues, prices, and liquidity (Gupta & Batra, 2016; Zimon, 2018), etc., and concurrently from a qualitative perspective: goals attainment, leadership style, employee behaviour (Anggadwita & Mustafid, 2014), client satisfaction (Alpkan In their study, Gopang, Nebhwani, Khatri, and Marri (2017) proposed a list of fourteen indicators to explain SMEs' performance, including their reputation, employee satisfaction, profits, productivity, prompt order delivery, sales, adequate working capital, product quality, achievement of targets, effectiveness in operations of production, clientele, decrease in product cost, product diversification, and ease of supervision.

Table 2: Number of Small and Medium Enterprises by State

STATE	NUMBER OF SMALL	NUMBER OF MEDIUM	TOTAL
ABIA	2,289	53	2,342
ADAMAWA	726	8	734
AKWA-IBOM	1,882	5	1,887
ANAMBRA	1,455	49	1,504
BAUCHI	2,209	32	2,241
BAYELSA	297	3	300
BENUE	1,783	28	1,811
BORNO	498	40	538
CROSS RIVERS	1,417	39	1,456
DELTA	1470	54	1,524
EBONYI	2,404	29	2,433
EDO	2,633	44	2,677
EKITI	926	2	928
ENUGU	1,404	28	1,432
GOMBE	876	28	904
IMO	1,976	44	2,020
JIGAWA	2,360	10	2,370
KADUNA	2574	76	2,650
KANO	2,298	143	2,441
KATSINA	1,335	32	1,367
KEBBI	809	6	815
KOGI	1,011	16	1,027
KWARA	1,398	18	1,416
LAGOS	8,042	354	8,395
NASSARAWA	2,586	18	2,604
NIGER	2,074	47	2,121
OGUN	2,394	71	2,435
ONDO	2,324	39	2,363
OSUN	2,995	12	3,007
OYO	6,039	92	6,131
PLATEAU	1,533	41	1,574
RIVERS	1,593	65	1,658
SOKOTO	691	161	852
TARABA	916	14	930
YOBE	99	3	102
ZAMFARA	1,222	14	1,236
FCT	2,750	75	2,825
TOTAL	71,288	1,793	73,081

Source: NBS-SMEDAN National Survey of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (Small scale business), 2017.

2.3 Microfinance Bank's Social Intermediation Vs Financial Intermediation Activities on the Performance of Small-Scale Businesses.

2.3.1 Financial Intermediation

- **Credit**

As per Water field and Duval (1996), credit is a type of getting cash with set terms for reimbursement. At the point when the profit from acquired cash surpasses the loan cost forced on the credit and there are insufficient collected reserve funds to back a firm. Acquiring makes more consistent than deferring organization movement until enough investment funds can be amassed. Assuming there is a method for taking care of the obligation. Credits are regularly given out for beneficial motivations, or to increment pay inside an organization. Advances for lodging, unique events, or utilization are likewise given by some microfinance establishments. Albeit numerous microfinance foundations request that main useful advances be allowed, any credit that increments family liquidity opens up big business profit, which can be reinvested in the business.

The two significant classes of individual and gathering procedures can be utilized to order credit conveyance techniques, as indicated by Water field and Duval (1996). Individual credits are at first dispensed to individuals given their ability to ensure reimbursement of the microfinance credits and a specific degree of safety. Second, bunch-based procedures make credit to gatherings; either to people who are individuals from a gathering and commonly promise each other's advances or to bunch that sub-loan to their individuals.

- **Payment Services**

According to Caskey (1994), deposit account holders have access to the traditional bank's check-writing and check-cashing services. Therefore, the banks' savings services and payment services are provided simultaneously. Similar payment services may be provided by microfinance banks either in conjunction with or independently from savings services for a fee. If financial services are used for payment. To pay for these services, microfinance banks can set their interest rates on customer deposit accounts unrealistically low. If not, a fee is levied to pay these expenses, which include staffing, infrastructure maintenance, and insurance costs. Fees may be a flat minimum price with additional fees for first-time clients, or they may be based on a percentage of the check's value. Furthermore, microfinance banks incur the risk that certain cashed checks won't be recoverable owing to inadequate money or fraud because they advanced funds on checks that must afterwards be cleared through the banking system. They also ensure interest expenses on the monies advanced. Therefore, to clear the check that is being cashed, microfinance banks need to be connected to at least one bank.

Payment services involve the sending of money from one place to another, in addition, to checking writing and cashing rights. Although the amount, microfinance clients frequently require transfer services.

- **Savings Mobilization**

According to the microfinance guidebook (2012), mobilizing funds is always met with administrative challenges, and the fees involved, particularly for modest sums, may not be desirable. It could be difficult for microfinance organizations to adhere to prudential rules and norms that concern deposit-taking institutions. Additionally, when microfinance Banks support lending activities, the volatility of the loan portfolios could put deposits at high risk. In other words, compared to a financial institution that solely offers to lend, a microfinance bank that also offers voluntary savings services creates a significantly different entity (Ekpete, and Iwedi,2017).

2.3.2 Social Intermediation

Because it provides mechanisms that allow beneficiaries to turn into customers who must be prepared to enter into a contract with reciprocal duty, social intermediation differs from other popular types of social welfare services. Individuals should eventually be prepared to establish strong commercial relationships with formal financial institutions through this part of social intermediation. For the offered financial services to be viable and sustainable, the procedure typically entails training members in fundamental accounting, financial management, and business planning. Through training in financial literacy, bookkeeping, and business administration for group members, social mediation encompasses group creation, networking, and capacity building (Mbaluka, 2013). MFIs can serve in this capacity as development tools in addition to banking. According to Bennett (1996), social intermediation is "a process wherein investments are made in the development of institutional and human capital to enhance the self-reliance of marginalized groups and prepare them to participate in official financial intermediation. But social intermediaries are employed for more purposes than only laying the groundwork for financial intermediaries (Zohir, and Matin, 2002). People have been helped via social intermediation through a variety of activities and capacity-building to become good savers and borrowers, manage their money or their financial groups better, and put whatever "social capital" they may have to more advantageous use (Kadagi, Ahmed, &Wafula, 2015). Due to this, MFIs are now focusing more on social security than financial security. MFIs have been successful at promoting group cohesion through networking by using "trust" as the foundation. The group members gain a variety of advantages, such as low-cost marketing, knowledge dissemination, and opportunity awareness (Hans, 2009). Social intermediation is not likely to be financially viable, according to Hans (2009). So, just like in the provision of services for financial intermediation, MFIs have embraced a range of techniques. Self-help groups (SHGs), individual banking programs in the form of joint liability groups, credit and saving cooperatives, or even SHGs, the Grameen model involving private borrowing but all borrowers belong to joint liability groups, or the mixed model involving Grameen and SHGs are some of the methodologies (Mbaluka, 2013). It's crucial to remember that MFIs are

private organizations whose main goal is to increase their profit while reducing costs which keep rising because microloans have expensive administrative fees. Although one of the MFIs' goals in providing social intermediations is to prepare people to engage in formal financial intermediation, as was previously said, this objective has positive externalities because it spreads information. While the availability of capital could be the main barrier to MSEs' expansion, there are other obstacles as well, like managerial and product market barriers that prevent their survival. The International Labor Organization (ILO) claims that MSEs are unlikely to survive and grow considerably without extra inputs to solve the additional obstacles (International Labor Organization, 2007). MFIs must consequently offer non-financial services to their clients, who are primarily MSEs.

Aspects of social mediation that MFIs can rely on include trust, sharing, engagement, educating and empowering, increasing confidence and capacity (including skills), gathering experiences from former clients and dormant groups, outreach to the most vulnerable, and so on. There is a theoretical rationale behind this that supports the operationalization of social capital like trust, commitment, loyalty, etc. in societal ties between micro-level institutions as well as between micro-level and macro-level institutions. Where neither conventional systems nor contemporary institutions can offer a foundation for trust, MFIs can do so through social intermediation. Social intermediation, however, differs from the delivery of social welfare services in that it permits "beneficiaries" to become clients capable of entering into a contract with reciprocal obligations. The level, nature, and time frame of the investment necessary for social mediation vary according to the obstacles that a certain client or target group must overcome. The degree of responsibility in financial intermediation that the client group is needed to or is willing to accept will also likely play a role. Institutions now have a tool other than financial intermediation to engage in and support microfinance as a result of social intermediation. It is a recognition of the reality that many low-income microfinance customers are unable to effectively utilize loans. Through a variety of activities and capacity-building, social intermediation equips people to handle their finances or those of their financial groups better, become good savers and borrowers, and put whatever "social capital" they may have to more advantageous use. Networking fosters the development of group cohesion and empowerment results from group cohesion. That is the appeal of microlending. Such interventions are a strong fit with the traditional qualities of NGOs because they entail close interaction with people at the grassroots level. Of course, the downside to such interventions is that they are unlikely to be financially self-sustaining. It is necessary to view them more as investments in human capital.

Finance for the poor's economic endeavours that produce/result in necessities of life is one way to combat poverty. To solve the challenges of poverty and access to other necessities of life including food, shelter, health, self-esteem, family planning, education, social support network, etc., the poor requires more than microfinance. Because they provide financial services along with other services, MFIs positively impact the lives of the poor and credibly contribute to their sustainable development and means of subsistence (Akingunola, Adekunle, Adegbesan, and Aninkan, 2013).

- **Group Formation**

Two or more individuals who are viewed as interdependent group members and who have common aims and stable relationships make up a group. At this moment, it is possible to say that people are interacting, either directly or indirectly. Small-scale enterprises would have a network that supports empowerment through microfinance group formation, group lending programs, and social engagement among members. They can depend on one another during difficult times, develop strong bonds with one another through their group, talk to each other about social concerns they may have, and share experiences to solve domestic and business issues. Through their group, they are also able to share valuable information about events in and around the community. These added benefits of group formation, which go beyond those of microcredit programs, are anticipated to further the empowerment of small-scale food manufacturing firms (Mohammad and Mohammed, 2007).

- **Skill Development**

This study looks at how small-scale manufacturers, in particular, can increase their abilities and confidence through group interaction, participation in decision-making, running meetings, and planning events. This section examines the expanded skills small business owners have acquired beyond those that are only related to loan and credit access programs and focuses more on social capital, especially in light of shifts in perceptions toward gender relations and appropriate behaviour for men and women. According to this theory, business owner's benefit from the intermediation activities of microfinance banks by gaining not only financial stability but also social confidence, being more autonomous, and having better tools to improve their company's condition (Bismark, 2017). These changes are sparked by the provision of independent sources of income for small business owners, which reduces their economic dependence on their counterparts; their exposure to diverse values and ideas through the intermediary of microfinance banks, which increases business owners' awareness of their rights; and the enhanced status of their business both in the household and the community as a result of their significant contribution to household needs.

- **Literacy Training**

Additionally, microfinance offers skill development to support and enhance the operations of small enterprises through efficient resource management, inventory control, financial literacy, and fundamental accounting practices. The microfinance training credit is typically scheduled on a weekly or monthly basis to assess the various enterprises and also serves as a period for loan payback. Accounting and financial literacy abilities will help business owners or managers make wise and unbiased financial decisions that could support the expansion of their companies (Sarpong-Danquah, Gyimah, Poku&OseiPoku, 2018). The majority of microfinance training services are often focused on strengthening beneficiaries' working capital and social life to boost productivity through the appropriate use of microcredit and other social services. (Dunford& Denman, 2001). The knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to adopt sound financial management strategies for earning, spending, saving, borrowing, and investing are taught through financial literacy training or education (Cohen,

Stack, and McGuinness, n.d.). Offering financial education may be advantageous to microfinance organizations. The improvement of personal finance knowledge, as well as the implementation of this information into action, are both facilitated by financial education. People who receive financial education are better prepared to make wise, timely decisions about their money and to believe that they can do so. The methods for responsible earning, spending, saving, borrowing, and investing are provided. Financial literacy enables individuals to better utilize the formal and informal financial services that are available to them and promotes financial behaviours that improve their overall financial well-being. The goal of financial education is to increase people's financial capacities so they can make wise financial decisions, including which financial services to employ in different situations or in an "enabling environment." In an enabling context that includes, but is not limited to, access to appropriate financial services, financial capability is the mix of information, skills, and self-efficacy needed to make and exercise financial management decisions that best match one's life circumstances (Henri, Fred, and Olive, 2015).

3. METHODOLOGY

The population of study comprise Small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Nigeria. But the study is limited to small-scale food manufacturing businesses within Lagos and Oyo State. A purposive method is used to select 747 small-scale food manufacturing businesses. Self - designed questionnaire was used to collect data from the owners of the small-scale food manufacturing business. To ensure validity and reliability, the researcher distributed copies of the questionnaire to the owners of small-scale industries in Lagos and Oyo states as a pilot test which captured small-scale business performance to sustain the objectivity of the study. Also, an expert judgment validity procedure is used in determining the suitability of the research instrument for this study. A pilot test which took the form of the test-retest method was conducted before the actual study. Simple percentage, Independent T-test, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC), and Multiple Linear Regression Analysis are employed to analyse the data.

Model Specification

Independent Variable A - (Social Intermediation): This variable will be measured using the following indices

MFSI (Microfinance Bank Social Intermediation) = (Group formation, Literacy training and Skill development).

Independent Variable B - (Financial Intermediation): This variable will be measured using the following indices. MFFI (Microfinance Bank Financial Intermediation) = (Working Capital Loan, Fixed Asset Loans, and Savings Collection).

Dependent Variable C – (Performance of small-scale businesses)

PSFMB (Performance of Small-Scale Food Manufacturing Businesses) = (Value Added, Value Chain, Customer Loyalty).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 3: Demographic Data of the Respondent

Variable	Categories	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	444	59.4
	Female	303	40.6
	Total	747	100.0
Age Group	Less than 20 years	6	0.8
	21 – 25 years	27	3.6
	26 - 30 years	141	18.9
	31 - 35 years	153	20.5
	36 - 40 years	104	13.9
	41 years and Above	316	42.3
	Total	747	100.0
Age of Business	1 - 5 years	305	40.8
	6 - 10 years	209	28.0
	11 - 20 years	155	20.7
	21 - 30 years	33	4.4
	31 - 50 years	45	6.0
	Total	747	100.0
Highest Education Qualifications	No Formal Education	6	0.8
	Primary Six Certificate	45	6.0
	S.S.C.E Certificate	155	20.7
	N.C.E/ N. D	209	28.0
	HND/ B.Ed./ B.Sc	269	36.0
	Master's Degree& Above	63	8.4
Total	747	100.0	
Business Insured	Yes	259	34.7
	No	488	65.3
	Total	747	100.0
Number of Employees	1 – 5	381	51.0
	6 – 10	240	32.1
	11 – 20	73	9.8
	21 – 30	41	5.5
	31 – 50	6	0.8
	50+	6	0.8
	Total	747	100.0
What is your average annual sales level?	10,000 - 50,000	33	4.4
	51,000 - 100,000	93	12.4
	101,000 - 250,000	96	12.9
	250,001 - 1,000,000	132	17.7
	1,000,000 - 2,000,000	154	20.6
	Above 2,000,001	239	32.0
Total	747	100.0	

Source: Field Survey Report, (2021)

Table 4: Microfinance Banks' Social intermediations influence the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria

	X	STD
Group formation	4.13	0.99
Literacy training	4.04	1.06
Skill development	4.26	0.94
Grand mean	4.14	0.99

Source: Field Survey Report, (2021).

The generalization of respondents on the effects of Microfinance Banks' social intermediation activities on the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria has shown in Table 4 shows a grand mean of 4.14 with a standard deviation of 0.99. Thus, the finding has a positive effect on social intermediation activities which include group formation, literacy training skills and skills development of business performance in Lagos and Oyo States.

Table 5: Microfinance Banks' financial intermediations influence the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria

	X	STD
Working capital	2.38	1.105
Fixed asset loan	2.704	1.414
General saving	2.652	1.293
Grand mean	2.652	1.293

Source: Field Survey Report, (2021).

In the general deduction, table 5 has revealed the extent to which Microfinance Banks' financial intermediation activities in the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria was concluded in Table 5 which shows a grand means of 2.65 with a standard deviation of 1.29 respectively. The responses from the items were negatively appraised by respondents based on individual perceptions in accessing loans without standing others to defend such capital in the study.

Table 6: T-test showing statistically significant difference in the effect of Microfinance Banks' study location (Lagos and Oyo States) on the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States

Variable	Study Locations	N	Mean	Std.Dev	Df	T-value	P	Remark
Performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses	Lagos State	397	56.8146	6.482	745	-.314	.556	Ho1 Failed to Accept
	Oyo State	350	56.969	6.988				

Source: Field Survey Report, (2021).

The table shows that there was a statistically significant difference in the effect of Microfinance Banks' study location on the performance of small-scale food manufacturing

industries in Lagos and Oyo States, $t(745) = -0.314$, $p > 0.05$. Hence, the research question is rejected, the result implies that there is a significant difference in Microfinance Banks' study locations (Lagos and Oyo States) on the performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector. The result further reveals Microfinance Banks' study location of Oyo State (mean = 56.969; S.D = 6.988) displayed higher tendency to engage in businesses than Lagos state (mean = 56.814; S.D = 6.482) in the distribution. The outcome connotes that Oyo State's performance in small-scale food manufacturing industries is slightly rated higher and visible compared to Lagos state in this study

Table 7: Summary of regression analysis for the significant difference of Microfinance Bank's social and financial intermediation activities on the performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria

a. Coefficients						
		Unstandardized Coefficients			Standardized Coefficients	
	Model	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1.	(Constant)	50.673	1.665		30.430	.000
	Social Intermediation	.089	.025	.134	3.578	.000
	Financial Intermediation	.010	.024	.015	.396	.692

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of small-scale sector

Source: Field Survey Report, (2021)

There is no significant relative difference in the effect of Microfinance Bank's social and financial intermediation activities on the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria. To test null hypothesis four, multiple linear regression analysis was used. In the analysis, the values of performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector were regressed on the values of Microfinance Bank's social and financial intermediation activities. The data for Microfinance Bank's social and financial intermediation activities (independent variable) was generated by summing responses of all variable items for both variables respectively while that of performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector (dependent) was generated by adding responses of all items used to measure the variable. The regression test results are presented in Table 6. The results of regression coefficients in table 6 revealed that at a 95% confidence level, a unit change in Microfinance Bank's social intermediation activities will lead to a 0.089% increase in the Performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector, given that all other factors are held constant. Also, at a 95% confidence level, a unit change in Microfinance Bank's financial intermediation activities will lead to a 0.10 increase in the Performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector in Lagos and Oyo State, Nigeria given that all other factors are held constant. This result suggests that Microfinance Bank's social intermediation has higher relative effects on the Performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector compared to Microfinance Bank's financial intermediation in the food manufacturing sector. On the strength of this result, the potent factor in this study was Microfinance Bank's social intermediation activities ($\beta = .134$; $t = 3.578$; $P > 0.05$); while Microfinance Bank's financial

intermediation activities ($\beta = .015$; $t = .396$; $P > 0.05$) is not a potent predictor as revealed in table 6. This study reveals that there is no significant relative difference in the influence of Microfinance Bank's social and financial intermediation on the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria.

5. CONCLUSION

Conclusion Based on the finding, it was concluded that Micro-Finance Banks' Social and Financial Intermediation functions have played a significant role in the development of the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in Lagos and Oyo States, Nigeria. It is essential to note that Micro-Finance Banks' Social Intermediation functions have positive effects and indeed contributed maximally to the performance of small-scale food manufacturing businesses in the studied states. Also, lack of experience in the business world, lack of appropriate managerial skills, poor financial discipline which crippled the performance of small-scale businesses, lack of self-discipline to control the intermediation fund from the financial institution which includes spending of working capital, and savings were seen as a setback from receiving appropriate supports from Micro-Finance Banks and the government-owned financial institutions Lagos and Oyo states in Nigeria. The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study: a) The MFBs should initiate regular social intermediations functions such as training and capacity-building programmes to assist small-scale business performance owners which would boost overall personal and economic growth for human productivities. b) Government should intervene to provide training centres that will give managerial training to the performance of the small-scale food manufacturing sector for business owners. This should be done in such a way that the attendance period is designed by the government representatives in collaboration with small-scale business owners" and union leaders and a valid and recognized certificate should accompany the training.

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